

Authors	Title	Year
L. Giovanini, D. Oliveira, H. Sanchez, D. Shands	Leveraging Team Dynamics to Predict Open-source Software Projects' Susceptibility to Social Engineering Attacks	2021
C. Pereira	NPM Package Security	2021
Alfadel, Mahmoud and Costa, Diego Elias and Shihab, Emad	Empirical Analysis of Security Vulnerabilities in Python Packages	2021
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S. Peisert, B. Schneier, H. Okhravi, F. Massacci, T. Benzel, C. Landwehr, M. Mannan, J. Mirkovic, A. Prakash, J.B. Michael	Perspectives on the SolarWinds Incident	2021
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BK. Pham, S. Chalishhafshejani	Automated software security activities in a continuous delivery pipeline	2021
P. Laplante	Software Labels	2021
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FL. Dennig, E. Cakmak, H. Plate, DA. Keim	VulnEx: Exploring Open-Source Software Vulnerabilities in Large Development Organizations to Understand Risk Exposure	2021
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M. Schaefer	Struggling With Supply-Chain Security	2021
J. Viega, JB. Michael	Improving Critical Infrastructure Protection by Enhancing Software Acquisition Process Through Blockchain	2021
J. Marjanović, N. Dalčeković, G. Sladić	Reproducible Builds: Increasing the Integrity of Software Supply Chains	2021
C. Lamb, S. Zacchiroli	2020 State of the Octoverse: Securing the World's Software	2021
N. Forsgren, B. Alberts, K. Backhouse, G. Baker	Windows Malware Binaries in C/C++ GitHub Repositories: Prevalence and Lessons Learned.	2021
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M. Taylor, R. K. Vaidya, D. Davidson, L. De Carli, V. Rastogi	Typosquatting and Combosquatting Attacks on the Python Ecosystem	2020
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P. Goswami, S. Gupta, Z. Li, N. Meng, D. Yao	Measuring and preventing supply chain attacks on package managers	2020
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A.F.H. Librantz, I. Costa, M.M. Spinola		

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S. Torres-Arias	In-toto: Practical Software Supply Chain Security	2020
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A. Zerouali, T. Mens, G. Robles	On the diversity of software package popularity metrics: An empirical study of npm	2019
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